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Modern development of the tourist sphere as a factor of economic security of the state

The article analyzes the development of the tourism sector from the point of view of the economic security of the national economy, which constitutes the most important part of national security and is a factor for the successful development of the state. The link between trends in the development of the tourism industry and general economic, technical and social achievements has been analyzed. It describes the importance of tourism in solving socio-economic problems and solving issues related to the improvement of the measures taken to increase the level of economic security in Ukraine.

Keywords: *national security, economic security, tourism, sustainable development, tourism potential.*

According to the Law of Ukraine “On the National Security of Ukraine”, the national security of Ukraine is the protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, democratic constitutional order and other national interests of Ukraine from real and potential threats [1]. This Law, in accordance with Articles 1,2,17,18 and 92 of the Constitution of Ukraine [2], defines the foundations and principles of national security and defense, the goals and basic provisions of state policy that guarantee protection

against threats to society and every citizen. In particular, Article 3 of the Law "On National Security of Ukraine" defines the fundamental national interests of Ukraine, which include the stable development of the national economy, civil society and the state to ensure the growth of the level and quality of life of the population.

Economic security is an essential part of national security and is a factor ensuring the successful development of the state. The problem of economic security of Ukraine is relatively new for domestic science - it has been the subject of research since the late 80s - early 90s, however, since that time it has been actively studied both in the scientific world and by the relevant executive authorities at the state level.

Economic security is a state of the national economy in which the protection of national interests, resistance to internal and external threats, the ability to develop and the protection of the vital interests of people, society, and the state are ensured. In this context, the vital interests are the set of needs that ensure the existence and progressive development of an individual, society, state [3].

Undoubtedly, economic security is the determining factor ensuring the successful development of the state. The main tasks of economic security are: ensuring proportional and uninterrupted economic growth, paying off inflation and unemployment, creating an effective economic structure and a developed securities market, reducing the budget deficit and public debt, ensuring social protection and improving the quality of life of the population, maintaining the stability of the national currency and tons .d These tasks determine the strategy of economic security as the formation and justification of strategic priorities, national interests, means and mechanisms for solving problems.

It should be noted that there are no detailed programs to ensure the economic security of the country as a whole and of individual sectors of the economy. Under these conditions, the basis of the state economic and national security strategy should be a development policy that would take into account strategic priorities, national interests and prevent possible dangers. The development of a program of priority

measures to ensure the economic security of Ukraine and practical steps in this direction should be based on a clear awareness of contemporary threats and risks. It is advisable to create special institutional bases for monitoring the economic security of Ukraine, studying existing threats and developing measures to maintain and strengthen the components of economic security.

In modern conditions, the tourism industry is becoming increasingly important in terms of the economic security of the national economy. In many countries, tourism plays a significant role in the formation of gross domestic product, the creation of additional jobs and the provision of employment, and the intensification of the foreign trade balance. Tourism has a huge impact on such key sectors of the economy as transport and communications, construction, agriculture, production of consumer goods, etc., i.e. acts as a catalyst for socio-economic development. In turn, the development of tourism is influenced by various factors: demographic, natural-geographical, socio-economic, historical, religious and political-legal.

There is a direct link between trends in the development of the tourism industry and general economic, technical and social achievements.

The demand for travel and tourism is determined simultaneously by market mechanisms (demand for tourist, excursion and other services, the supply of these services and their distribution), and exogenous variables, i.e. factors that are not directly related to tourism and travel, but have a significant impact on the degree and form of demand for tourism activities. Exogenous factors include demographic and social changes, economic and legal achievements, the development of trade, transport infrastructure, information technology and increased safety of travel.

Demographic and social changes include: population aging, earlier retirement with adequate retirement benefits, increasing number of single adults, increase in the number of working women, families with two working family members, a tendency to later marriages, increase in the number of childless families, an increasing period paid vacation, a better understanding of travel opportunities and care for the environment.

The growing standard of living in the developed industrial countries of the world leads to an increase in the length of employee vacations and a fairly high level of pension coverage, which has a significant impact on the development of tourism.

Economic development of tourism is characterized by impressive data on the global economic market. They show that tourism is the fastest growing industry in many countries of the world and that its role in the global economy is constantly growing. Today, the share of tourism is about 10% of the world national product (GNP), 11% of world consumer spending, 5% of total tax revenues, 7% of world investment and a third of world trade in services.

Modern tourism is a complex and mass phenomenon, a form of recreation, a way to learn about the world, the area of interregional and international cooperation, services and business, a part of regional and state policy. For such a complex socio-economic system as tourism, the solution to the issue of economic security is primarily manifested through its sustainable development. Moreover, the safety of tourism development and sustainable development of tourism are identified with each other, which in our opinion is a positive trend. Sustainable tourism will be able to cope with the negative effects of tourism development and enhance its positive effects. Sustainable development of tourism involves its planning and management, ensuring the improvement of the quality of life of the local population, protection of the natural environment and cultural heritage.

Today, the secret of success of most popular tourist centers is based on a clean environment, effective measures to protect it and the identity of the local culture, a high level of organization of the tourist process, quality assurance and safety. In places that do not have this set of qualities, there is a decline in the level of service and a decline in the volume of tourism. These competitive advantages can become a reality for those tourist destinations that have adopted the principles of sustainable development of tourism as the basis for their development.

The basis of sustainable development should be based on such economic mechanisms that, on the one hand, lead to the efficient use of natural resources and the preservation of the environment, and on the other, to meet the needs of people and improve the quality of life of not only living but future generations.

In tourism, environmental pollution in places intended for recreation means the loss of the most important positive qualities of a tourist product and, consequently, a decrease in its competitiveness, and subject to a significant excess of the maximum permissible concentrations of harmful substances, the impossibility of its further use for tourist purposes. Economic and environmental problems are thus closely interconnected, and they cannot be overcome in isolation from each other. Environmental degradation leads to economic, and vice versa, improving the state of the environment makes it possible to solve economic problems in various countries, including through the development of international tourism. In this case, it is especially important to form the right strategy for the development of the tourism industry, aimed at preserving these resources and ensuring a safe future for this destination.

Tourism in Ukraine at the state level is recognized as a priority area of the national economy. The functioning of the tourism market depends on the livelihoods of many sectors of the country's economy, as well as 10-15% of its population. It is also important to note that tourism is one of the few areas of activity in which the attraction of new technologies does not lead to a reduction in the number of employees. The cost of creating one job in this area is 20 times less than in industry, and the turnover of investment capital, compared to other sectors of the economy, is 4 times higher.

According to the Deputy Minister of Economic Development and Trade of Ukraine M. Titarchuk: "by the end of 2017, the share of the tourism industry in Ukraine amounted to 1.5% of GDP, and the total budget from tourism and related industries (services, food, transport) 2017 received 39.6 billion UAH. "[4]. In 2018, the country's budget was replenished by more than 90 million UAH tourist tax, which is almost 30%

more than a year earlier. Tax payments from tourism have also increased. In total, revenues from tourist tax and tax payments in the tourism sector increased to 4.2 billion UAH, or 20.7%, which was facilitated by the growth in domestic tourist flows, the effectiveness of implementing decentralization, and the increase in local fiscal discipline.

For comparison, the share of trade in Ukraine's GDP is 14% or 218 billion UAH, the processing industry - 12.4%, agriculture (including forest and fish) - 10.2%, transport - 6.4% [5].

The analysis shows that the contribution of tourism to the economy of Ukraine and its individual regions remains insignificant today, and the country's tourism balance has been passive for many years now. This is partly explained by the fact that in Ukraine, the pace of development of outbound tourism increasingly exceeds that of entry tourism, and Ukrainian tourists spend more and more money on holidays outside Ukraine, developing foreign resorts and tourist centers, which ultimately stimulates the socio-economic development of these countries. This passivity is also explained by the low level of development of social and domestic tourism, which in the conditions of the total decline in the payment capacity of the population has recently begun to revive due to the lack of opportunities to realize their tourist potential, even in the context of opening borders and receiving a long-awaited visa-free regime.

More than 70% of tourists who bought vouchers in 2016, ordered trips abroad. According to the State Statistics Service, there were 2 million of such people (against 1.6 million in 2015). In total, 453.6 thousand Ukrainians bought tourist trips in Ukraine. Although it should be noted that the domestic "voucher" tourism has grown (in 2015 there were only 357 thousand people). Domestic Ukrainian tourists prefer to explore the cultural, historical and gastronomic sights of Kiev, Lviv, Poltava, Cherkasy and Dnipropetrovsk regions.

According to the State Border Service, there are qualitative changes in the structure of foreign tourist flow. Tourists from Western European countries that do not

have common borders with Ukraine began to come to Ukraine more often. In the first place - the Spaniards, who showed an increase of 68%. Following are tourists from the UK (47.3%), Lithuania (23.4%), Italy (15.4%), Germany (13.3%) and France (9.2%). Indian tourists overtook the Chinese (+57.4 and 38.8%, respectively). The Japanese have become more - they are quite a bit behind the Chinese with the indicator of 38.3%. At the level of 21.7%, an increase in the flow of Israeli tourists was recorded, despite the "border wars". Even the number of Americans has increased among foreigners who choose Ukraine as their holiday destination - by 19%. In addition, according to the data of Ukrainian mobile operators, in 2018, 22.3 million movements of foreign subscribers in Ukraine were recorded [7].

The growth of inbound tourism is caused by a whole complex of factors. This includes visa liberalization, an increase in the number of budget and convenient direct flights, as well as the intensification of Ukraine's promotion in the international tourism market. The most popular among foreigners of the region are Transcarpathian and Odessa. Interestingly, the Kharkiv region is becoming a popular center for business tourism.

Ukraine has sufficient regional potential for the formation and development of tourism, but the lack of effective management in this area is a deterrent to the realization of this potential. The development of tourism in any region can be carried out in the presence of the main components: recreational resources, infrastructure, personnel, capital, management system. All this underlines the importance, including economic support, of the development of domestic tourism. Despite the fact that in recent years, domestic tourism has had positive development trends, it has not yet reached the level observed in most developed countries of the world. Along with tax incentives and effective accounting support for the industry, there are issues of ensuring the safety of tourists, the environment and information.

In regions with high tourism potential, where the development of tourism is properly regulated and relies on a system of effective state support, income from

tourism can be one of the most significant sources of livelihood for the local population and the preservation of cultural and natural heritage. Inbound tourism has a direct and indirect impact on the development of a whole range of sectors of the local economy, causing additional effective demand in the destination, generating incomes of enterprises and households, employment, taxes to budgets of all levels, providing foreign exchange inflows and a positive balance of foreign trade, which increases its social and economic benefits. However, for the effective development of inbound tourism, it is necessary to take seriously the image of a destination and to ensure a correspondingly high level of competitiveness of Ukrainian destinations at the international level.

Possessing rich cultural, historical and natural resources, the country faces the challenge of creating a modern tourism industry that can attract foreign and domestic tourists and increase the share of the tourism industry in the GDP structure of Ukraine.

According to the State Statistics Committee, in 2016 there were 3506 legal entities and individual entrepreneurs providing travel services in the tourist market of Ukraine. At the same time, according to official statistics, in this structure 80% are travel agents who work on the terms of commission, as a rule, up to 10%. In 2016, tour operators and travel agents sold 1.6 million vouchers for a total amount of UAH 27.4 billion, which is 36% (10.1 billion UAH) more than a year earlier. At the same time, their income amounted to UAH 11.5 billion, which is 63% higher than in 2015 (UAH 4.23 billion). But operating expenses also increased by 55% and amounted to 9.14 billion UAH. in 2015. These are the data of the State Statistics Service, obtained from 500 companies (20% of licensed tour operators).

The tourist market began to recover after a sharp drop in 2014-2015 (in 2014 it fell by 40%, and in 2015 by another 20%, the number of tour operators decreased by 10%). Ukrainians are slowly moving away from the oppressive state caused by war and crisis. The situation is gradually stabilizing, and the tourism market responds to

this as a living element. But while tourism has not yet returned to pre-crisis indicators, although it has optimistic forecasts for the end of the year [6].

Thus, tourism is among the most effective and promising industrial complexes that should not be neglected, especially when solving social and economic problems and solving issues related to improving the measures used to increase the level of economic security in Ukraine.

The importance of tourism for the sustainable development of the economic system of Ukraine is difficult to overestimate: it undoubtedly reduces the risks of the domestic economy, diversifies it, positively affects its global image and competitiveness. At the same time, tourism itself was and remains a very vulnerable type of business, experiencing the direct or indirect impact of a practically unlimited number of factors, both external and internal.

The solution of a number of economic, organizational, social, legal problems should contribute to the rise of tourism in Ukraine, increase its contribution to the national economy, increase its ranking in world tourism arrivals, especially since the country has the most powerful potential for this.

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